

1 **Discrimination of latent disease in TB in the T circulating memory cell.**

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7 To understand the molecular basis of latent disease in humans with tuberculosis infection, we measured
8 total gene expression in CD4 T cells from healthy individuals and humans with latent TB infection.
9 Humans with latent TB, in the T-cell, expressed very little *Tnfsf8* as compared to healthy individuals. The
10 CD4+ T cell of patients with latent TB displayed induction of *Ccl20* and *IL411*, but silenced *Ccr7*. Latent TB
11 with associated with silencing of *Arhgef3* with concomitant activation of *Arhgef39*.

12 Citations

- 13 1. Jasmer, R.M., Nahid, P. and Hopewell, P.C., 2002. Latent tuberculosis infection. New England
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